

EPIC-SHIFT

Funded by
the European Union

Website

DELIVERABLE 7.1

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EPIC-SHIFT

Funded by
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Project no. Grant Agreement 101181470

Project acronym: EPIC-SHIFT

Project title: Securing Holistic and Impactful Food Systems
Transformation with Novel Foods based on alternative proteins

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-01

Start date of project: 1.11.2024

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable title: Project Website

Date of deliverable: 28.02.2025

Deliverable Lead Partner: EIT Food

Dissemination level: Public

Comment

The website was launched as expected by the end of month 4 of the project, on February 28, 2025. It features the target page layout, including a brief description of the project, its objectives, and contact information. It is expected that this version of the website will further developed with the feedback from the consortium to serve in the best possible way the project's needs. As the project progresses, materials will be uploaded to the website.

Description

The EPIC-SHIFT project website can be accessed at <https://epic-shift.eu/>. The aim of the website is to communicate the project and its results, enable effective communication between project partners and external stakeholders, and provide up-to-date information regarding EPIC-SHIFT's progress, as well as easy access to project results, reports, and publications.

The website has been designed to allow the lead partner in WP7 to update dedicated sections such as News & Events, Results (Publications, Deliverables, Newsletters) through a Content Management System. Additionally, updates to other content have been enabled to allow any future refinement of key messages and other content reflecting outcomes and conclusions from various engagement and co-creation activities with EPIC-SHIFT stakeholders conducted by project partners across different Work Packages and Tasks.

Given that stakeholder mapping is currently ongoing and a stakeholder engagement strategy will be developed and implemented in the coming months, the website retains scope and budget for further modules to be added. These modules will reflect the subsequently established requirements and goals defined by the strategy and be addressed to relevant EPIC-SHIFT target groups. Reflecting the project's multi-stakeholder approach, the website features two types of contact forms, which serve as an open invitation for any interested parties to express their interest in collaborating on the project

Main navigation bar and landing page

Main navigation bar has been organized in 5 main pages for a clear user-friendly experience. Home page (also landing page) presents a basic information about the project and has the aim to quickly present what the project is about and what the website can bring to the visitor.

About

About page contains following sections:

Mission

Partners

Our work

News & Events

It is a section devoted to news about the project and project partners as well as to events attended or organized by EPIC-SHIFT.

Results

The page *Results* is a repository of project publications, deliverables and newsletter archive

Media

This page has a space for the *media kit* where materials such as press releases, logo, style guide and project brochure will be available for download. Media page will invite as well to sign-up for the newsletter.

Contact button

After clicking the contact button, a section with two different contact forms appears: one for organizations wishing to join the project's stakeholder network, and the other for individuals who simply want to stay informed.

The screenshot shows the website's navigation menu with links for Home, About, News & Events, Results, and Media. Below the menu is a banner with the text "Looking to get in touch?" and an image of a meal. The main content area is titled "Contact options" and features two side-by-side contact forms. The left form is for organizations and the right form is for individuals. Both forms include fields for Name, Email, and Message, and a "SEND MESSAGE" button.

Home About News & Events Results Media

Looking to get in touch?

Contact options

Are you an organization who wants to join the EPIC-SHIFT network?

Name *

Email *

Message *

SEND MESSAGE

Are you an individual who wants to get informed?

Name *

Email *

Message *

SEND MESSAGE

Page footer

Displays EU flag, funding statement, disclaimer, and contact details. It also includes button linking to project social media.

Join our newsletter for latest updates in protein science

Name *

name@example.com

SIGN UP

Project Coordinator

Deniz Koca
Project Coordinator

Visit us on LinkedIn